

Calibration System of the 5-Axial 3D Printer

Master Thesis

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List of Abbreviations

Chapter 1 Introduction

The first 3D printing technology introduced in the late 1980s. Even then, by the end of the 2000s, 3D printing technology was still expensive and primarily used among industries. In 2004, Adrian Bowyer invented the idea of RepRap as an open-source and self-replicating 3D printer. After that, Bowyer and his University of Bath teammates designed early prototypes of 3D printers based on this idea. In January 2009 the very first commercially available 3D printer was launched for sale, in running condition and developed on the RepRap design. This printer used Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) more generally known as Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM). FDM printers create layer-by-layer structures from the bottom-up approach, by heating and extruding material on a build base.

This meant a major milestone for 3D printer technology, in which 3D printers became widely viable. Throughout this, 3D printing technology has become widely known. Including inexpensive and self-made printers have emerged using various 3D printing technologies. Nowadays, FDM printers are the most common 3D printers. That's most probably because FDM printers are consumer-friendly, can print durable parts and are relatively inexpensive.¹

FDM printers do have such drawbacks, like precision and their difficulty to print overhanging objects without additional support.¹ The performance can be increased to some degree by adjusting the layer height and using a thinner nozzle. Although this precision of these techniques is improved, there might be difficulties for printing layers that are not perpendicular to the printing bed. But with this, the printing time for a structure will also be increased. As an example, by decreasing the layer height from 0.6 mm to 0.3 mm, the number of layers will be doubled as well as the printing time will also roughly doubled. Same as for a thinner nozzle, printing time will also increase as the amount of material the printer will extrude will be significantly decreased.² Time is often a concern while using support to print overhanging shapes, as the supports need additional work for the FDM printer.

¹ SD3DPrinting. FFF vs. SLA vs. SLS: 3D Printing. 2013. URL: <http://sd3d.com/fff-vs-sla-vs-sls/> (visited on 25/08/2020)

² Volcano - Print Faster, Stronger, Bigger. E3D-ONLINE. 2014. URL: http://e3d-online.com/blog/volcano_release (visited on 25/08/2020).

Subtractive manufacturing is the opposite of additive manufacturing. CNC mills are a modern technique which uses the subtractive manufacturing technique. CNC mills are functioned in the same manner as FDM printers, except they extract materials from the work-piece instead of adding it. For CNC mills, the ground problem overcome in three ways: various types of cutting tools, tool paths that regulate movement in three axes rather than just two and a half. Tool paths movement in three dimensions cannot be the solution for FDM printers, and tools are not an alternative for FDM printers.

In multi-axis CNC mills, the issue has been overcome by turning a work-piece or tool, thus the tool can work from multiple angles. A most popular multi-axis design when dealing with various structures is a 5-axis CNC mills. The drawback of FDM printers is that the objects are still from bottom to up form printed. By turning either the nozzle or the printed part, as in 5-axis mills, these factors may impact.

Therefore, this thesis will concentrate on the calibration system of 5-axial 3D printer, which specifies the end-stop and the homing of additional axes and development of a temperature control system for the hotend using a micro-controller and attaching it to the control unit.

1.1 Motivation

However, 5-axial 3D printing is in the early stages of development and offers tremendous advantages for additive manufacturing across the globe by using a more effective 3D printing technique. Activities to integrate this concept could also be found in the CNC mills.

Right now, 3-axial 3D printers are based on the 2-axial movement of the Printing bed and 1-axial movement of the nozzle/extruder. The transformation of the 3-axial printer into a 5-axial printer can be brought by different ways of developments that can significantly change 3D printing processes later on.

There are many functional/prototypes of 5-axial 3D printer available by different developers. Some of these are:

- **DMG Mori:** On 6 September 2016, DMG Mori posted a video³ of a hybrid system capable of processing both subtractive and additive metal. This

³ 1DMG Mori 5-axis hybrid: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s9ldZ2pl5dA>

system has a table/table set up and can change its function based on the type of tool it uses.

- **TWI:** On 14 November 2014, TWI posted a video⁴ of a 5-axis Laser Metal Deposition (LDM) printer for metal. The printer also uses a table/table set-up and uses the LDM technology developed by TWI to print the metal. Information on this printer has been also published for the general knowledge on the TWI website.⁵
- **5axismaker:** A video⁶ of the 3D printer capable of their system was released on June 10, 2015. This system has a head/head set-up.

5-axis 3D printers do exist, but either knowledge about them is hard to find or is still under progress. This is why the key inspiration for this thesis comes from 5-axis CNC milling machines, as it is a more developed area and better known.

1.2 Objectives

The report is aiming for the development of the method to calibrate two axes (B&C) and the development of a temperature control system for hotend to improve the printing process and printing quality.

In order to achieve the goal, this study aimed to:

- Construction of a 5-axis 3D printer
- The calibration system of 5-axial 3D printer, end-stop and homing.
- Analyzing various methods/possibilities based on the principle of trial and error including theoretical and practical experiments.
- Implementation of the most acceptable and efficient calibration method for additional axes.
- Development of the temperature control system to control the temperature of the extruder.

1.3 Outline of the thesis

This thesis is divided into three parts: Introduction, Project, and Conclusion. The three sections are again split into six chapters: Introduction, Overview of the 3D

⁴ TWI 5-axis LDM machine: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yKnImfuMSgo>

⁵ <https://www.twi-global.com/media-and-events/insights/revolutionary-development-cuts-manufacturing-times-using-laser-metal-deposition-cuts-manufacturing-time>

⁶ 5axismaker printer: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=w8F18L4yk8M>

printer, Calibration system, Development of the temperature control system, Results and discussion, Conclusion and future outlook:

- The chapter "**Overview of the 3D printer**" discusses the relevant information for this thesis, some of the analysis related to this topic is given. This chapter also describes the tools and programs used to carry out this thesis.
- The chapter "**Building a 5-axial 3D printer**" describes the design and construction of 5-axial 3D printer. This chapter is divided into three sections. The first section relates to the design and development of the first prototype and then to issues with it. The second section relates to the design and development of the second prototype. The last section describes the calibration of two additional axes.
- The chapter "**The temperature control system**" describes the design, planning and development of the temperature control system and then programming for this system is explained.
- The chapter "**Result and discussion**" discusses and analyses the outcome and solution.
- The final chapter "**Conclusion and Future outlook**" concludes this thesis, accompanied by suggestions for future study.

Chapter 2 Overview of the 3D printer

The background hypothesis is presented in this chapter. There is also some analysis of the key elements of this thesis.

Additive manufacturing is a technique in which the data of a digital 3D model is used to make the 3D object layer by layer, by extruding the specific material. The material used in the additive manufacturing process can be metal, fluid, plastic or even paper.^{7 8} The material selection depends on the additive manufacturing process that is being in used as per requirement.

2.1 Construction of 3D printer

To grasp the design and development of a 5-axis system, a 3-axis 3D printer that is extensively developed and widely in use must be understood first.

2.1.1 Types of 3-axis 3D printer

3-axial 3D printers exist in multiple different configurations, the three most common types being:

- **Cartesian type**

The 3D Cartesian printers consist of three rails which move along the axes of the Cartesian plane. Managing the movement of a Cartesian 3D printer is relatively easy physically and software-wise since there is only linear motion along the axis.⁹ The set-up and operation of a Cartesian 3D printer are illustrated in Figure 2.1.

- **Polar type**

The polar 3D printers consist of 2 linear and one rotational movement axes. On the horizontal rail, the printing bed moves along Y-axis and on the vertical rail, the extruder moves along Z-axis. There are the printing bed can rotate 360° and that consists of X-axis. Due to this, it is more complex to position the extruder, because there need to define the polar coordinates for X-axis. An

⁷ 4

⁸ 57

⁹ 10

illustration of the configuration and movement of a Cartesian 3D printer can be seen in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1 Type of the 3-axis 3D printer¹⁰

- **Delta type**

The Delta 3D printers typically consist of three vertical rails standing in a triangular formation. The extruder is attached to these rails with three arms, and the movement of the extruder is accomplished by pushing them up and down. Due to this, it is more complicated to determine the extruder position, which makes Delta printers more sophisticated software-wise.⁹ The set-up and operation of a Delta 3D printer can be seen in Figure 2.1.

2.1.2 Overview of 5-axial system

When a system does have more than 3 axes, it is known as a multi-axis system. With that, the system also operates in rotational movement (ABC) and parallel motion (UVW) over X, Y, or Z, as shown in Figure 2.2. (ABC) describes the rotational movement around the axis, and (UVW) defines the parallel movement along the axis. For example, the extruder may rotate along the X-axis and the work-piece may rotate along the Z-axis.

¹⁰ <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Growable-Robot-with-Wakimoto-Takamori/f01bc8d1936287ab6a7b9f96c2cd69a5dcb672f0>

Figure 2.2 Designations and directions of multi-axis systems¹¹

The 5-axis CNC machine is the most commonly adopted multi-axis systems for the manufacturing of specific parts when high accuracy is required.¹² The two additional axes of the 5-axis configuration happen to be rotational. These rotations are sometimes obtained either through turning a tool/extruder along any axis or by rotating the table where the work-piece is connected. The 5-axis system may also have three distinguishable configurations:

- **Table/Table configuration**

Table/Table configurations are the most common method of multi-axis systems. In the table/table method all rotation is done with the work-piece. That operates as tables rotating around the X-, Y-, and Z-axes. As so the object is rotating around the tool. So the rotating table of the system must be capable of bearing the weight of the object.^{Error! Bookmark not defined.}

- **Head/Head configuration**

In the Head/Head configuration, all rotary operations are carried out by the tool head of the system. This system can be either vertical and/or horizontal. Since both rotational axes are in the head, the entire head can be modified, which allows various actions to be accomplished depending on the design of the head.^{Error! Bookmark not defined.}

¹¹

https://books.google.de/books?id=Ws228Aht0bcC&printsec=frontcover&source=gbs_ge_summary_r&cad=0#v=onepage&q&f=false

¹² Why 5-Axis? Hurco. URL: <http://www.5-axis.org/index.php/why5-axis-benefits-of-switching-to-a-5-axis-machine/> (visited on 10/09/2020).

- **Head/Table configuration**

Head/Table configurations are a mixture of the above two set-ups. Head/Table systems have one rotational axis at the head and the other at the table. Head/Table systems are potentially the most powerful of these three configurations and can be used to process heavy parts.^{Error! Bookmark not defined.}

2.2 Toolpath generation

Tool path generation is the most essential technology for CNC and 3D printing. The tool path from a 3D model has to be generated to be able to create a structure. This is done by slicing the object into horizontal layers. The more layers the object is sliced into, the more detailed final output will be. However, the printing or milling of the object can take a long time as the number of layers increased. Theoretically, the orientation of the tool may be any point on the Gauss Sphere. In order to increase machine performance and consistency, the tool position at each step of the process should be optimized.¹³ The process from the 3D model to a sliced model can be seen in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3 Illustration of slicing of 3D model

2.3 G-code

The G-code was initially established by the Electronics Industry Association (EIA) in the 1960s.¹⁴ The G-code defines what the system is meant to do with the command lines. That /adjust the system configuration, to set it in different modes,

¹³

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/225871485_Tool_path_generation_and_simulation_of_dynamic_cutting_process_for_five-axis_NC_machining [accessed Sep 7 2020].

¹⁴ J. Dong. Rapid Response Manufacturing: Contemporary methodologies, tools and technologies. Manufacturing Systems Engineering Series. Springer US, 2012. ISBN: 9781461563655. URL: <https://books.google.no/books?id=FGTIBwAAQBAJ>.

or to command it where to set the position of system tool. This is achieved by a combination of the G-code command G01 / G1 with X, Y, Z, F, where X, Y and Z are the destinations the tool should travel to in the Cartesian coordinate system, which can be in mm or inch. The feed rate (F) determines the speed of the process, that should be should be as mm/min or inch/min.

2.3.1 G-code for 5-axial system

The 5-axis G-code has all the features of the standard G-code, but it furthermore manages the movement of the extra rotational axes. The most specific way to control rotation is by adding A, B and C to the G-code. The A, B and C describe rotation angles, an example of which can be seen in Figure 2.2. As A, B and C are used to describe rotational axis in a system, the G-code may depend on the system configuration on which the G-code is generated. When describing the rotation as C145, the system will determine-axis it can rotate to that angle based on its specification. Whenever a 5-axis tool path is programmed in the CAM system, the system already calculates the movements.

As Mach3 has been used to sends to G-code to controller unit here in this project, Mach3 can define the rotary axes directly from the software. That's why the G-code for 5-axial system via Mach3 should be G-code command with X, Y, Z, A, B, C. Where X, Y and Z are the destinations the tool should travel and A, B and C are the angular value.¹⁵

2.4 Homing and End-stop

In 3D printers, end-stops are used in all moving axes. Two primary purposes of end-stops in 3D printers are axle reference system and safety.

After powering the 3D printer, the controller board of the 3D printer does not know the position of each axis. So the system must first determine the starting point for the physical coordinate system, this process called *Homing*.¹⁶

The other essential use of an end-stop is preventing the damage of hardware. If any movement tries to reach the physical limits of the machine, the end-stop will stop the movement.¹⁶

¹⁵ <https://machmotion.com/cnc-info/g-code.html>

¹⁶ <https://marlinfw.org/docs/hardware/endstops.html#configuring-endstops-and-probes>.

The end-stops should be hardware and/or software in the machine.

The hardware end-stops are like a simple switch, it directly connects to the end-stops ports of the controller board. So it sends the signal to the controller board as criteria met. Some most common end-stops are shown in figure 2.4 (Mechanical end-stop, Optical end-stop and Magnetic end-stop).

Figure 2.4 Types of end-stops: Mechanical end-stop, Optical end-stop and Magnetic end-stop (Left to right)^{17 18}

Normally, 3D printers are only fitted with hardware end-stops on one side of an axis. This is used to establish the starting point (origin) of the unit coordinate system, as discussed above.

In order to prevent the damage at another side of the axis, the firmware defines the software end-stop. This can be calculated as the maximum distance between the actual end-stop and so the system can command stop the axis.

2.5 Calibration system

Each parameter plays a significant role to obtain the targeted output for a 3D printer. If the 3D printer is not accurately calibrated, it may also give bad output.

Most of the time, it guides the part for greater precision. Without precision, the models apparently cannot be of use anymore. And, this can be accomplished only when the printer is well calibrated. The configurations shall specify the measurements of the 3D printer against the norm to have a good outcome of the system.¹⁹

¹⁷ <https://octopart.com/ss-5gl-omron-3346>

¹⁸ <https://www.aliexpress.com/item/32818879300.html>

¹⁹ <https://pick3dprinter.com/3d-printer-calibration/#proper-deposition-of-first-layer>

There are some of the steps that need to be calibrated before starting the printing:

2.5.1 Calibration of the Stepper motor

Stepper motors are the components that control the axes and extruders to move the precise distance. In the 3D printer, the relationship between the steps taken and the distance currently travelled can be directed by calibration of stepper motors.

2.5.2 Calibration of an extruder

The extruder must be depositing the right quantity of filament all time. For that, the right value for steps per mm needs to be obtained.

2.5.3 Calibration of the Axes

As each axis has end-stop, with that the home position or starting point for each axis can be defined. The end-stops of X- and Y-axis can be seen in figure 2.5. Now to calibrate the movement of each axis, the distance of travel for each axis from end-stop can be calibrated. This is similar to calibrating the extruder. To do so, the stepper motor of each axis would have to be calibrated as the number of steps taken by the stepper motors for moving 1 mm along X, Y, and Z directions, respectively.

Figure 2.5 The end-stops of X- and Y-axis

2.5.4 Calibration of hotend temperature

The perfect method to figure out the printing temperature is by printing a temperature tower. The tower has been built with multiple sections created at various heights.¹⁹

Besides, each section needs a different printing temperature for the best output. To obtain that, sometimes the G-code needs to be changed for each section. As a consequence, the final output can be evaluated for the best-adapted temperature.

2.6 Tools and programs used

This section explains the tools and programs used for this research.

- **Novusun NVEM V2**

NVEM V2 is the 3-6 axis motion controller board by company Novusun.

NVEM V2 facilitates the use of Mach3 software and standard MPG to connect with a computer using Ethernet.²⁰

The ARM design framework is adopted by the NVEM V2 motion controller. It has photoelectric isolated 12 input ports and 10 output ports interface for ordinary digital data, and 1 port 0-10V spindle speed analogue output interface. It has two 12v output too. That can also change as PWM output. It can support 3-6 axis stepper motor systems with 200 kHz pulse output capacity for each axis.²⁰ The NVEM V2 board can be seen in figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6 Novusun NVEM V2 controller board

This board needs 12-32VDC/0.5A to power up. The Novusun NVEM V2 is a CNC controller board used in this project.

²⁰ https://www.nvcnc.net/pdf/NVCNC_NVEMv2_EN.pdf

- **NEMA 17 stepper motor**

In this project, NEMA 17 stepper motors are used to control both axes and extruders. The stepper motor is propelled by a magnetic gear with several teeth attached to the rotor. Although the magnetic force depends heavily on the air distance between the magnets, a small step size can be obtained. The stepper motor has 3 aspects to get the movement input; full step, half step, and micro-step. The half step has a double-resolution over a full step, but the average torque is smaller. NEMA 17 is 200 steps per revolution/half step stepper motor.²¹

Figure 2.7 NEMA 17 stepper motor

- **Arduino UNO**

Arduino Uno is an ATmega328P based microcontroller board. It has 14 optical input/output pins (6 of which can be used as PWM outputs), 6 analogue inputs, a 16 MHz ceramic resonator, a USB port, a power jack, an ICSP header and a reset button.²² Arduino Uno can be seen in figure 2.8.

²¹ <http://www.mosaic-industries.com/embedded-systems/microcontroller-projects/stepper-motors/specifications>

²² <https://store.arduino.cc/arduino-uno-rev3>

Figure 2.8 Arduino UNO board

Arduino UNO is used to control the hotend temperature in this project.

- **AutoCAD**

AutoCAD is a commercial computer-aided design (CAD) and designing software framework, developed by Autodesk. AutoCAD was first released in December 1982 as a desktop application operating on microcomputers with internal graphics controllers.²³ AutoCAD has mostly used design 2D geometry and 3D models with solids, surfaces and mesh objects.²⁴ AutoCAD is used to design the 3D printer in this project.

- **Mach3**

Mach3 is a software by a company named Artsoft. Mach3 makes a standard computer into a controller for a CNC system. Mach3 can work with Windows PCs to control the movement of the motors by processing G-Code. Although it has many advanced features, it is customizable and useful for many systems with a variety of hardware types.²⁵ Mach3 is used to connect and command the Novusun NVEM board and to send the G-code to the board via computer.

- **Arduino IDE**

The Arduino IDE is an open-source software from Arduino. It includes a text editor for writing code, a message field, a text console, a toolbar with typical feature buttons and a variety of menus. Connects to Arduino board to access

²³ <http://www.fundinguniverse.com/company-histories/autodesk-inc-history/>

²⁴ <https://www.autodesk.de/products/autocad/overview?plc=ACDIST&term=1-YEAR&support=ADVANCED&quantity=1>

²⁵ <https://www.machsupport.com/software/mach3/>

programs and interact with them.²⁶ It supports the Arduino language, which is a set of C/C++ functions that can be called from the code. Arduino IDE is used to program the Arduino UNO board in this project.

- **Fritzing**

Fritzing is an open-source PCB designing software. Fritzing was initiated at the FH Potsdam and is now developed by the Friends-of-Fritzing foundation.²⁷ It includes many electronic components and with the help of that, it's very easy to generate a layout of PCB design. Fritzing is used to design different PCBs in this project.

²⁶ <https://www.arduino.cc/en/guide/environment>

²⁷ <https://fritzing.org/>

Chapter 3 Building and calibration of the 5-axial 3D printer

5-axis systems consist of three different configurations: table/table, head/head and head/table, as described in section 2.1.2. The key factors for the decision to choose a head/table set up in this project are:

- Two additional axes will have the extra weight of these extra motors to be added. These motors must be added to the X-and Y-axis in the head/head or table/table configuration. This could be more complicated than fitting an additional motor to the Z-axis that the head/table system requires.
- The head/head or table/table configuration must be compact at the head to operate efficiently. This would make it difficult for the system to integrate and rebuild. Whereas the head/table system can be conveniently built as the weight is spread along with the head and table for additional motors.
- As mentioned in section 2.1.2, another advantage of a head/head or head/table system over a table/table system is that it can able to work with heavy work-piece.
- One of the issues with the table/table is the attachment of the work-piece. This may be a matter of printing on a table/table system since it could be difficult to add an attachment to a part that is being printed. If the work-piece rotate around the X or Y axis, it may be detached from the table during printing.
- Another issue that could occur with the arrangement of the head/head and table/table is that the system can be unstable as both additional motors attached to one component (head or table).

3.1.1 Determining the origin of the machine

The origin of two rotary axes do not intersect in the head/table configuration, and the most suitable location of the centre of the device would be where the rotary axes intersect.²⁸ Therefore, the origin needs to be defined, and both axes need to be aligned accordingly. A diagram of the point of intersection of axes in the head/table configuration can be seen in Figure 3.1, where the origin is at the centre

²⁸ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260296649_Design_and_implementation_of_five-axis_transformation_function_in_CNC_system

of the print bed. The purpose to have the origin at the centre of the table is to simplify both the programming of the firmware and to make a G-code.

Figure 3.1 Diagram of the intersection of axes in the head/table configuration in the first prototype

Two prototypes were made while constructing a 5-axis 3D printer. The design of these versions will be discussed in this part. The issues with the first version and the justification for making a second version will also be discussed in this chapter.

3.2 Design of the first prototype

In the first prototype, the head/table configuration has two parts, one is for the print bed and the other is for the extruder. The axial illustration of this concept can be seen in figure 3.1. For the rotational print bed, the rotary system would add on top of the intersection of X- and Y-axis. That provides movements in X and Y-axial direction and 360° rotational movement around the Z-axis to the print bed. To make this possible an extra motor had to be added on the top of the intersection of rails of X and Y-axis. Because of the X and Y-axial movement of the rotational print bed, it needs to be smaller. The Z-axis had to be extended to compensate for the height of the motor in the rotary system of the printing bed. As shown in figure 3.1 it is convenient to keep the origin of the printing bed at the point where the X and Y axes intersect. To make sure this is the case the design of the rotary system should be designed with the print plate in focus. On the base of axial illustration of this concept the first prototype has been designed, that can be seen in figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2 Illustration of the first prototype

For the rotational head/extruder, the rotary system would add on the top rail where the extruder attached, that has the only movement along Z-axis. The rotary system of the head gives the rotational movement to the extruder around Y-axis. As the extruder hangs on the top rail, it can move -90° to $+90^\circ$ below the top rail. As shown in figure 3.1 it is convenient to keep the extruder at a horizontal position and with the centre point of the print bed align.

3.2.1 Design of the platform

While designing the platform, several methods to create the attachment between the rotary system and the platform were considered. To drive the rail of X-axis, there are two motors has been added to both sides of the platform. The reason for that is to move the rail synchronous from both sides and to give stable and accurate movement in X-axis. The same method has been also applied to Y-axis, two motors drive the rail in Y-axial movement. The setup of both axes can be seen in figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3 Design of the platform in the first prototype

For the movement of rails there are all motors placed perpendicular and it drives the rail through the rubber belt system. To make sure the platform is rigid, a support structure is created on the top and the bottom of the platform to stabilize the structure. Both rails are intersecting, that intersection is used to move the print bed. This setup is also suitable to implement the rotary system on the table on that. The result of the platform can be seen in Figure 3.3.

3.2.2 Design of a table rotary system

As mentioned in section 3.2, when designing a table rotary system, the printing bed should be in focus. The system should also have the capacity to calibrate the printing bed. In order to achieve this, the attachment for the rotary mechanism consists of an attachment part which can be positioned at the intersection of the X-axis and the Y-axis rails. The stepper motor directly drives the rotating table so the attachment section for the stepper motor was made, the C-axis was able to rotate freely from 0° to 360° around the Z-axis, which can be seen in figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4 Front and top view of attachment with a table rotary system

In this system, the print bed is connected to the stepper motor which then attaches with rails of X and Y axis so the motors transform the rotation to the C-axis. The attachment that connects the motor with the intersection of rails, is fixed with both rails. The rails pass through attachment part so the attachment slides on the rails. As the motor placed underneath the attachment and motor shaft positioned over the rails, the print bed can be placed parallel to the Z-axis and does not make any contact with the rail. That can be seen in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5 Attachment with X- and Y-axial rails

3.2.3 Design of a head rotary system

As mentioned in section 3.2, when designing a head rotary system, the position and alignment of extruder also should be in focus. In order to rotate the extruder around B-axis, the mechanism for the head rotary system consists of the stepper motor and attachment of that with the top rail which can be driven by the stepper motor of Z-axis. The stepper motor that rotates the extruder is fixed on below the rail, so in this system, the extruder cannot move in X and Y direction. It can only move in Z-axial direction towards the printing bed. As the extruder is directly

connected to the extruder to rotate it, the stepper motor is placed along Y-axis that can be seen in figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6 Design of a head rotary system

The attachment section for the stepper motor was designed, so the stepper motor placed beneath the rail and extruder can be towards the front of the rail. As extruder positioned ahead so it can be freely rotated from -90° to $+90^\circ$ around the Y-axis, the side view of this section can be seen in figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7 Side view of a head rotary system

3.3 Problems with the first prototype

Since experimenting with the first prototype, there appeared to be some issues.

- As X- and Y-axial movements are based on the belt system, those movements are not precise enough. The belt can be stretched and cannot make enough grip with gear compare to screw rod system, it is a breakdown of this system.
- There is a head rotary system on the top rail, so the Z-axial movement is also not stable enough. It is because of the extra weight of head rotary system there.
- As mentioned in section 3.2.1, two motors have been placed to drive each axis(X and Y). Because of that, there is not enough room for placing the electronics component of the system.
- As this is the first prototype, it has been build step by step and so the build quality is also not good enough. That's why during the printing process the printer is shaking and the result is not accurate enough.
- Overall the printer isn't stable enough. The final result of the first prototype can be seen in figure 3.8.

Figure 3.8 The final result of the first prototype

Due to the problems mentioned, specifically, the movement problems of the X-, Y- and Z-axis, the first prototype was not able to print accurately with the 5-axis system. It was then determined to modulate a new prototype where these issues were taken into consideration.

3.4 Design of the second prototype

The first prototype shows that the first configuration had some problems with the application of the belt system to the X-and Y-axial movement, and also with the unstable movement of the top rail. One solution to solve for this issue was to develop a new system with a screw-based movement on each axis. The first prototype also had an issue with the orientation of the table rotary system and its placement at the intersection of the X-and Y-axis rails, which could be changed by adjusting the positions of the X-and Y-axis rails. The location of the extruder rotary system on the first prototype also created a restriction of the rotational movement extruder in the B-axis, as it attached directly below the top rail. For eliminating this limitation, the head rotary head system had to be redesigned. Two of the possible changes would be to position the head rotary system on the front of the top rail and minimize as much of the framework as possible from the platform and the rotary table system.

Figure 3.9 Diagram of the intersection of axes in the head/table configuration in the second prototype

In the second prototype, the head/table configuration has divided into two parts, one is for the print bed and the other is for the extruder. The axial illustration of this concept can be seen in figure 3.9. For the rotational print bed, the rotary system has been attached to the rail of Y-axis. That provides the movement in Y-axial direction and 360° rotational movement around the Z-axis to the print bed. To make

the rotation possible an extra motor had been added with the mount that attached with Y-axis. With this setup, the print bed moves along Y-axis only instead of X and Y both. Because of that, size of the print bed can be increased than the first prototype. The Z-axis has been designed more robust to convey the weight of the head rotary system as well as the X-axial rail. As shown in figure 3.9, it is convenient to keep the centre of the printing bed at the point where the X and Y axes intersect as an origin.

For the rotational head/extruder, the rotary system has been added on the X-axial rail, with this setup the extruder can move along X- and Z-axis. The rotary system of the head gives the rotational movement to the extruder around Y-axis. As the extruder attached on the top rail, it can move more than -90° to $+90^{\circ}$. As discussed above, it is convenient to keep the extruder perpendicular to the print bed and align with the centre point of the print bed.

Figure 3.10 Illustration of the second prototype

With those new configurations and changes, the second prototype has been designed. An illustration of a second prototype can be seen in figure 3.10.

3.4.1 Design of the platform

As mentioned in section 3.3, one of the issues with the first prototype was that the X-and Y-axial movements are based on the belt mechanism, but these movements were not accurate enough. To prevent this problem, to an X-and Y-axis screw-based mechanism has been implemented. As the screw-based system applied, there was only one motor required to drive each X-and Y-axis. Because of that one more issue has been solved, that was to have some space for electronics components on the platform. One major adjustment was made, which was the implementation of the X-axis on to the Z-axis. Due to all this, the arrangement of the Y-axis on the platform and the X-axis on the top rail of the Z-axis had to be redesigned to accommodate this.

To address the problem of the unstable Z-axis, there were two screw-based mechanisms for this function, those driven by motors. But to fix this problem, two extra rods have been placed beside both shafts to ensure smooth and stable movement. The design and configuration of the second prototype can be seen in figure 3.11.

Figure 3.11 The design and configuration of the second prototype

3.4.2 Design of a table rotary system

Due to the new configuration, both the B-axis mount and the C-axis mount had to be redesigned. The result of the table rotary system can be seen in figure 3.12. In the first prototype, the configuration of the table rotary mechanism is more complicated due to its position on the intersection of the X-axis and the Y-axis, and thus the result was not sufficiently consistent and precise. To compensate for this, the X-axis was relocated to the upper portion of the printer and connected to the Z-axis. The table rotary system has only a Y-axial linear movement, so it has a simple mount to attach the table rotary system to the Y-axial rail. It was easier to create a more robust fastening mechanism by doing this. Due to this, the diameter of the printing bed can be expanded since there is no movement in the X-axis.

Figure 3.12 The design of a table rotary system of the second prototype

To accomplish this, the rotary mechanism consists of an attachment element and a stepper motor that drives the print bed such that the mount segment to attach the stepper motor with Y-axis has been made. The C-axis was free to turn 360° around the Z-axis, as can be seen in Figure 3.12.

3.4.3 Design of a head rotary system

As stated in section 3.4, a new configuration of the head rotary system for the installation of the B-axis was developed, as can be seen in figure 3.13. In the first prototype, the head rotary mechanism is mounted to the rail, so there is only one linear movement in the direction of the Z-axis. As the X-axis was relocated to the upper section of the printer and connected to the Z-axis, the head rotary mechanism is now attached to X-axis and can move along the X-axis and Z-axis. As described in section 3.4, the entire linear axis mechanism has been changed with two rods on both sides of the screw-based mechanism, allowing a more precise and reliable movement of the X-and Z-axis head rotary system. In this configuration, the extruder can be positioned at any point on the X-Z plane.

Figure 3.13 The design of a head rotary system of the second prototype

The head rotary mechanism consists of the attachment part used to mount the stepper motor to drive the B-axis, the mounting section for the stepper motor has been redesigned as per the new configuration of the X-axis. The extruder can be rotated from -90° to $+90^\circ$ in B-axis, as can be seen in Figure 3.13.

3.5 Calibration of additional two axes

In the early stages of the project, it was decided to use the Novusun CNC board, and because it only operates with Mach3, all the calibration was conducted on Mach3. Mach3 can operate 6 axes simultaneously as per the configuration of the controller board in use. Therefore it was possible to focus on the two additional axes. The second prototype was developed at the beginning of this thesis.

The second prototype was designed to make the calibration of the two additional axes simpler. The X- and Y-axis mechanisms were designed to align the centre of the printing bed with the extruder.

As mentioned in section 1.1, the inspiration for this is the 5-axial CNC system. This was an obvious area to look at before determining how the device could understand the G-code and the G-code format. As mentioned in section 2.3.1, the

CNC 5-axis defines its cutter position (CP) by using the format as G-command with X Y Z A B C in Mach3. In this format, X, Y, Z are the linear coordinates of the CP, and A, B, C are the angular coordinates of the tool. By using this G-code format, the component is presumed to be set and the tool can complete all movements. This makes it possible to generate a G-code that will operate on various 5-axis systems as long as the device converts the G-code to function in its setup.²⁹ Whenever the object is static, therefore the G-code is easier to grasp and thus easier to control or write manually.

As mentioned in sections 3.1.1 and 3.4, the origin of the system had to be defined at the centre of the printing bed. The position of each linear axis was therefore also specified in compliance with the necessity of the position of origin. The calibration of linear axes has to be accurate to calibrate additional axes because the calibration of the additional axes is based on the linear position too. To do so, the end-stop and the homing position of linear axis also had been defined to make easy calibration of additional axes.

3.5.1 Calibration of B-axis (Head)

To calibrate the head rotary system, the homing must be positioned perpendicularly and aligned to centre of the print bed. As the linear movement of the head rotary system depends on the X-axis, the calibration of the X-axis needed first. The configuration of the head rotary system on the X-axis can be seen in Figure 3.14. The total length of the X-axis (X_{Total}) is 296 mm. The end-stop of the X-axis needed 12 mm from the left-end, so the head rotary system is always 12 mm apart from the left-end of the X-axis. The end-stop configuration for the X-axis can be seen in Figure 3.15. The width of the mounting section (H_{width}) to be mounted the stepper motor is 60 mm, so the X-- limit is 42 mm apart from the end-stop of the X-axis. The end-stop configuration for the B-axis can also be seen in Figure 3.17. It required 20 mm at the right end of the mounting section, so the X++ limit is always 50 mm away from the right-end of the X-axis.

²⁹ Karlo Apro. Secrets of 5-axis machining. Industrial Press Inc., 2008.

Figure 3.14 The configuration of a head rotary system on the X-axis

Figure 3.15 The end-stop configuration for the X-axis

It is possible to find the applicable travel distance of the head rotary system on the X-axis (X_{Jog}), by using the distance of X-- limit from left-end of an X-axis (X_{Left}) and X++ limit from right-end of an X-axis (X_{Right}) as shown in Eq. 3.1.

$$(X_{Jog}) = (X_{Total}) - [(X_{Left}) + (X_{Right})] \quad \text{Eq. 3.1}$$

$$(X_{Jog}) = 296 \text{ mm} - [42 \text{ mm} + 50 \text{ mm}]$$

$$(X_{Jog}) = 296 \text{ mm} - 92 \text{ mm}$$

$$(X_{Jog}) = 204 \text{ mm}$$

So, the applicable travel distance of the head rotary system on the X-axis is 204 mm. Because the extruder must be in the centre of the print bed, the origin of the B-axis must also be aligned with that. After calibration of the X-axis precisely done, it was easy to position the head rotary system at a specific point or position on the X-axis. The home position (X_0) of the X-axis was then defined at 152 mm from the left-end and 144 mm from the right-end side of the X-axis. So the head rotary system has 110 mm jog distance in X- direction and 94 mm jog distance in X+ direction.

The determined values for the homing and soft limits (maximum and minimum) of all linear axes had been calibrated in mach3 to achieve a precise output for the calibration of the rotary axes. The home position for each linear axis was established in order to obtain the position of the additional axes as needed to coordinate with the origin of the system. The soft limits have been defined as how far each axis can jog in both directions. The configuration of the soft limits and the home offset of all axes on Mach3 can be seen in Figure 3.16.

Figure 3.16 The configurations of the soft limits and the home offset of all axes on mach3

After defining the homing position on the X-axis and the positional calibration of the head rotary system has been accomplished, the angular calibration has been conducted. To do so, the B-axis was defined as the rotary axis in mach3 and an optical end-stop on the right side of the head rotary device has been installed for reference and homing purpose. The rotational movement of an extruder around the B-axis and the orientation of the end-stop can be seen in Figure 3.17.

Figure 3.17 Rotational movement of an extruder and the orientation of an end-stop

The installation of the end-stop on the B-axis was quite complicated due to the limited space on the head rotary structure and thus the configuration of the B-axis was marginally adjusted to make it 180° applicable. The end-stop used for the B-axis is almost identical to the end-top of the other axis. As mentioned in section 2.5, an optical end-stop works on 5V, because of that the voltage converter module was designed to use it. That module can convert 5V pulse to 12V, the design and configuration have been described in Appendix B. It sends a signal to the controller board when the extruder is located parallel to the X-axis on the right side of it. This has been defined as a B-limit and at 180° a B++ limit has been configured. The perpendicular position (Centre of B-- and B++) was defined as the home position (B0) of the B-axis. The configuration of both soft limits and home offset can be seen in Figure 3.16. As a result, the extruder has a rotational movement of 180° around the B-axis and can be aligned with the centre of the print bed during the homing process.

The unit of B-axis is considered in degree, because of the B-axis was defined as a rotary axis in Mach3. Mach3 rotates the motor by steps per unit. The number of steps Mach3 must be sent to the motor so that one unit of movement (inch or mm or degree) depends on the properties of the stepper motor and the micro-stepping or electronic equipment in the drive electronics. The NEMA 17 stepper motors have been used on both rotational axes. The basic resolution of the NEMA 17 stepper motors is 200 steps (as a complete step) per revolution (1.8° per step) and 400 steps (as a half step) per revolution (0.6° per step).

The micro-stepping drives have a various number of micro-steps configuration. In this project, 16 has been fixed to get precise output. A value of 16 micro-steps determines that Mach3 need to send 3200 pulses per one revolution for a stepper axis drive (NEMA 17 stepper motor with a resolution of 200 steps/rev). The step angle of the stepper motors with 1/16 micro-step for each step is 0.1125°.

Now as the required motor revolution per unit of travel has been defined, Steps per unit for Mach3 has been calculated as shown in Eq. 3.2.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Steps per unit} &= \frac{\text{Mach3 steps per revolution}}{\text{Total number of unit per revolution}} && \text{Eq. 3.2} \\ &= 3200/360 \\ &= \mathbf{8.888889 \text{ steps per degree}} \end{aligned}$$

From the calculation, the steps per unit value were derived and defined in the motor tuning section of Mach3, which can be seen in Figure 3.18. As in Mach3, this value doesn't have to be an integer, so it provides much accuracy.

Figure 3.18 Configuration of B-axis motor

For the system to understand the G-code, it has to compute the distance between the hotend and the print bed from the angular value of B-axis. To determine that distance, Mach3 need the radius of the B-axis too. Figure 3.19 indicates the configuration of the radius of the B-axis in Mach3. The radius of B-axis (r_b) is 55.6 mm, which can be seen in Figure 3.17.

Rotation Radius	
A	+0.0000
B	+55.6000
C	+110.0000

Figure 3.19 Configuration of radius of B- and C-axis in Mach3 (in settings function)

With that, Mach3 can represent a Cartesian coordinate as a polar coordinate system, as shown in Figure 3.20. Where $I = X$ and $Z = K$. Because the radius of an axis is always constant in the system it is possible to find the actual position of the hotend in XZ plane by using the relation between Cartesian coordinates and polar coordinates as shown in Eq. 3.3.^{30 31} By setting $X = I$, $Z = K$ and $r_b = 55.6$, Eq. 3.4a and Eq. 3.4b becomes Eq. 3.5a and Eq. 3.5b. Where θ is the angle of the B-axis. Since the head rotary system has a range of -90° to $+90^\circ$, the sin and cos

³⁰ George B. Arfken, Hans J. Weber and Frank E. Harris. *Mathematical Methods for Physicists*. Seventh Edition. Academic Press, 2013. ISBN: 978-0-12-384654-9. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780123846549000037>.

³¹ Eric W. Weisstein. *Spherical Coordinates*. 2014. URL: <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/SphericalCoordinates.html> (visited on 1/10/2020).

function is being used to determine the actual position (I, K) of the hotend in XZ plane, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** and Eq. 3.6b.

$$r_b = \sqrt{X^2 + Z^2} \quad \text{Eq. 3.3}$$

$$\theta = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{Z}{r_b}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 3.4a}$$

$$\theta = \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{X}{r_b}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 3.4b}$$

$$\theta = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{K}{55.6}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 3.5a}$$

$$\theta = \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{I}{55.6}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 3.5b}$$

$$K = 55.6 \times \cos \theta \quad \text{Eq. 3.6a}$$

$$I = 55.6 \times \sin \theta \quad \text{Eq. 3.6b}$$

Figure 3.20 Visualization of polar coordinates, based on the Wolfram MathWorld model³¹

This is how the system with Mach3 can control the G-code format from a linear axial coordinate system to a rotary axial coordinate system. The conversion for the B-axis can be seen in Figure 3.21.

Figure 3.21 The conversion for the B-axis

3.5.2 Calibration of C-axis (Print bed)

To calibrate the table head system, the homing must be aligned to the extruder. This process is almost similar to the calibration of the head rotary system, as the linear movement of the table rotary system depends on the Y-axis, the calibration of the Y-axis needed first. The configuration of the table rotary system on the Y-axis can be seen in Figure 3.22. The total length of the Y-axis (Y_{Total}) is the same as X-axis, 296 mm. The end-stop of the Y-axis also needed 12 mm from the back-end, so the table rotary system is always 12 mm apart from the back-end of the Y-axis. The width of the mounting section (T_{width}) to be mounted the stepper motor is also 60 mm, so the Y++ limit is 42 mm apart from the back-end of the Y-axis and Y-- limit is 30 mm from the front-end. The end-stop configuration for the Y-axis can be seen in Figure 3.23.

Figure 3.22 The configuration of a table rotary system on the Y-axis

It is possible to find the applicable travel distance of the table rotary system on the Y-axis (Y_{Jog}), by using the distance of Y++ limit from the back-end of a Y-axis (Y_{Back}) and Y-- limit from the front-end of a Y-axis (Y_{Front}) as shown in Eq. 3.7.

$$(Y_{Jog}) = (Y_{Total}) - [(Y_{Back}) + (Y_{Front})] \quad \text{Eq. 3.7}$$

$$(Y_{Jog}) = 296 \text{ mm} - [42 \text{ mm} + 30 \text{ mm}]$$

$$(Y_{Jog}) = 296 \text{ mm} - 72 \text{ mm}$$

$$(Y_{Jog}) = 224 \text{ mm}$$

Figure 3.23 The end-stop configuration for the Y-axis

So, the applicable travel distance of the table rotary system on the Y-axis is 224 mm. Because the centre of the print bed must be aligned to the extruder, the origin of the C-axis must also be aligned. After calibration of the Y-axis precisely, it was easy to position the table rotary system at a specific point or position on the Y-axis. The home position (Y_0) of the Y-axis was then defined at 154 mm from the back-end and 122 mm from the front-end of the Y-axis. So the table rotary system has 112 mm jog distance in Y- direction and 92 mm jog distance in Y+ direction.

As mentioned in section 3.5.1, the configuration of the soft limits and the home offset of the Y-axis on Mach3 can be seen in Figure 3.16.

After defining the homing position and the positional calibration of the table rotary system has been accomplished, the angular calibration has been conducted. To do so, the C-axis was defined as the rotary axis in mach3 and the end-stop below the rotary head system was intended to be mounted for reference and homing. The first sensor had been tested to use as the end-stop is CNY70, it is a reflective

sensor that combination of an infrared emitter and phototransistor. The second sensor was the optical end-stop, which has been used in all other axes.

The CNY70 is a reflective sensor that combines an infrared emitter and phototransistor in a leaded package and also able to blocks visible light. The common use of the CNY70 sensor is to calculate rpm of the shaft or motor. It can detect a light mark on a dark background or vice-versa. So the idea was to use this sensor is to have a dark mark on the backside of the print bed and detect it. With that, the system can get the precise angular position of the print bed. During the testing of this sensor, it was able to detect up to 1.5mm wide line. The result can be seen in Figure 3.24.

Figure 3.24 The result of CNY70

The accuracy of the CNY70 was not enough to get the precise position of the print bed, and it can be more inaccurate when the rotation speed of the print bed rotates is high.

Because the optical end-stop involves an obstruction to work, the use of the optical end-stop requires a modification in the design of the print bed. The issue may occur with the use of the optical end-stop when the print-bed has to be changed in the system, then each time it needs to be designed as per the end-stop requirement.

During the calibration of the head rotary system, the centre of print bed has been defined as an origin and home position of the system, therefore the angular position of the print bed is not much essential during the homing process. Mach3 can consider the angular position of the print bed as a zero position and can rotate it in both directions (-360° to $+360^\circ$). Therefore the configuration of max- and min- limit of the C-axis has been done without any end-stop. That can be seen in Figure 3.16. As a result, the print bed can rotate 360° around the Z-axis and the centre can also be aligned with the extruder during the homing process.

The unit of C-axis is considered in degree, because of the C-axis was defined as a rotary axis in Mach3. As mentioned in the calibration of the head rotary system, Mach3 rotates the motor by steps per unit. The steps per unit value were the same as the B-axis because the same stepper motor and the micro-stepping driver has been used on both rotational axes. The step angle of the stepper motors with 1/16 micro-step for each step is 0.1125° and the value of steps per unit 8.888889 (steps per degree) has been calculated as shown in Eq. 3.2. The steps per unit value were configured for the C-axis in the Mach3 motor tuning section, as can be seen in Figure 3.25.

Figure 3.25 Configuration of C-axis motor

For the system to understand the G-code, it has to compute the distance between the hotend and the centre of the print bed from the angular value of C-axis. With that, Mach3 and system can manage the rotational speed of the print bed during the printing at a different radius. To determine that distance, Mach3 need the radius of the C-axis too. Figure 3.19 also indicates the configuration of the radius of the C-axis in Mach3. The radius of C-axis is 110 mm, which can be seen in Figure 3.23.

As all 5-axis works together, Mach3 can represent a Cartesian coordinate as a spherical polar coordinate system, as shown in Figure 3.26. Where $I = X$, $J=Y$ and $Z = K$. As mentioned in section 3.5.1, Because the radius of B-axis is always constant in the system it is possible to find the actual position of the hotend and radius of C-axis (r_c) in a sphere by using the relation between Cartesian coordinates and spherical polar coordinates as shown in Eq. 3.8^{30 31}. By setting $X = I$, $Y=J$, $Z = K$, Eq. 3.9a and Eq. 3.9b becomes Eq. 3.10a and Eq. 3.10b. Where θ is the angle of the B-axis and Φ is the angle of the C-axis. The sin and tan function is being used to determine the actual position (I, J, K) of the hotend in a sphere and a radius of C-axis, as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**, Eq. 3.6b, Eq. 3.11a and Eq. 3.11b.

Figure 3.26 Visualization of spherical polar coordinates, based on the Wolfram MathWorld model³¹

$$r_b = \sqrt{X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2} \quad \text{Eq. 3.8}$$

$$\Phi = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{X}{Y}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 3.9a}$$

$$\Phi = \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{X}{r_c}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 3.9b}$$

$$\Phi = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{I}{J}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 3.10a}$$

$$\Phi = \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{I}{r_c}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 3.10b}$$

$$J = \frac{I}{\tan \Phi} = I \times \cot \Phi \quad \text{Eq. 3.11a}$$

$$r_c = \frac{I}{\sin \Phi} = I \times \csc \Phi \quad \text{Eq. 3.11b}$$

This system has two rotational axes rotate along Y-axis and the Z-axis. Transformation matrixes in Eq. 3.12 and Eq. 3.13³² have a rotational transition around Y and Z. With these, the device can convert the G-code format from a linear axial coordinate system to a rotary axial coordinate system and vice versa. The C-axis conversion can be seen in Figure 4.2.

Figure 3.27 The conversion for the C-axis

$$R_{(Y,B)}(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 & -\sin \theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Eq. 3.12}$$

$$R_{(Z,C)}(\Phi) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \Phi & -\sin \Phi & 0 \\ \sin \Phi & \cos \Phi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Eq. 3.13}$$

From multiplying these matrixes, the transformation matrix derived, as seen in Eq. 3.14 and Eq. 3.15. So the transformed coordinates $\{X', Y', Z'\}$ can be calculated by multiplying this matrix with the original coordinates $\{X, Y, Z\}$, seen in Eq. 3.16.

³² M.W. Spong and S. Hutchinson. Robot Modeling and Control. Wiley, 2005. ISBN: 9780471649908. URL: <https://books.google.de/books?id=wGapQAAACAAJ>

$$T = R_{(Y,B)}(\theta) \times R_{(Z,C)}(\Phi) \quad \text{Eq. 3.14}$$

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta \cos \Phi & -\sin \Phi & -\sin \theta \cos \Phi \\ \sin \Phi \cos \theta & \cos \Phi & -\sin \Phi \sin \theta \\ \sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Eq. 3.15}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} X' \\ Y' \\ Z' \end{bmatrix} = T \times \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Eq. 3.16}$$

As a result, after calibration of all axes, the extruder and print bed positioned at the home position (origin) of the system by linear movement of X-, Y- and Z-axis, and by rotational movement of B- and C-axis. Both B- and C-axis provides rotational movement as per the G-code input on Mach3 to work the printer as 5-axial.

3.5.3 Overall Calibration

Before it is possible to print with the system the machine coordinate system (MCS) origin must be obtained. As mentioned in section 3.1.1, the origin has to be at the centre of the print bed. After defining the origin, the distance of the hotend from the print bed has to be also calibrated. This was done by using the Z-axial movement.

After the head rotary system has been calibrated in X- and B-axis; and the table rotary system has been calibrated in Y-axis, the hotend move towards the centre of the print bed and adjusts it so that the hotend at the assigned intersection point is barely touching the print bed.

As Print bed must be aligned horizontally too, for that it needs to be fixed accurately on C-axis. To calibration of horizontal alignment of the print bed must be done until 360° rotation of the C-axis with the hotend barely touching the centre of the print bed and then the print bed moves to a point along the Y-axis, for example, Y = 40, and then the hotend move down till the hotend barely touches the print bed. Then the same procedure must be done with the opposite side of the Y-axis, in this example Y = -40. This process must be continued until the hotend barely touches the print bed at a minimum of two Y-axis points.

Chapter 4 The temperature control system

The temperature control system (TCS) for the extruder is explained in this chapter. This chapter includes the planning and development of TCS.

4.1 Planning the temperature control system

The typical 3D printer controls the temperature of the hotend using the controller unit. Usually, the temperature control algorithm within the controller reads the temperature from the thermistor and then controls another pin attached to the MOSFET that activates or deactivates the power from the extruder.

As the Novusun NVEM CNC controller board has been used for this project, it does not have a built-in temperature control system. So, the temperature control system in the first prototype was based on the manual control unit.

As mentioned in section 2.6, Novusun NVEM has a single analogue output port (0-10V) to control the spindle speed, which can also be used as a PWM output. The spindle feature of the Novusun NVEM board was planned to be used as a TCS for the second version. To do so, it was necessary to first understand how the spindle function operates on the controller board and how it runs the spindle.

4.1.1 Spindle function of Novusun NVEM board

The spindle function unit of the Novusun NVEM board is shown in Figure 4.1. It has five pins: GND, VSO, INDEX, OUT1, OUT2, for spindle speed function.²⁰

Figure 4.1 The spindle function unit of the Novusun NVEM board

- GND is the common ground pin, OUT1 and OUT2 are the common output pins. OUT1 and OUT2 pins are normally used for the clockwise and counter-clockwise directions.

- VSO is the only analogue output pin, providing 0 to 10v output. The output of the VSO is $10v \cdot S / S_m$. where the S is the spindle speed and the S_m is the maximum spindle speed, this can be controlled by the S directive or the Mach 3 spindle speed setting feature. For e.g., if the maximum spindle speed (S_m) is 1000, the current spindle speed is $S=650$, then the VSO output voltage is $10 \cdot 650/1000=6.5V$.
- INDEX is a spindle speed input pin for feedback.

The main advantage to use the spindle function to control the extruder temperature is S directive. The S-directive also being in use to control the temperature in the typical 3D printers. Therefore it can be easy to define the temperature in G-code of printing object.

By setting the maximum spindle speed as a maximum temperature that requires for the hotend, the S-directive can be defined to set the temperature in G-code. For e.g., when the maximum spindle speed has been set to 300 rpm, then the maximum temperature is 300 °C defined, therefore, by different S- directive in G-code a VSO gives the output as shown in Table 4.1.

G-code	Spindle speed	Hotend Temperature	VSO output
S 300	300 rpm (S_m)	300 °C (T_m)	10 V
S 250	250 rpm	250 °C	8.33 V
S 100	150 rpm	150 °C	5 V
S 50	50 rpm	50 °C	1.67 V

Table 4.1 Hotend temperature (°C) and Output (V) at VSO at Different S-directive in G-code

As the maximum temperature required for this project is 300 °C, the maximum spindle speed was as 300 rpm defined. The configuration of spindle speed in Mach3 can be seen in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2 The configuration of spindle speed in Mach3

4.1.2 INDEX function of Novusun NVEM board

INDEX is a spindle speed input pin to get feedback. Mach3 can display real-time spindle speed by INDEX function when the INDEX pin gets one pulse at each revolution, for that the pulse voltage must be 6V-10V. For this project, it needed to show the real-time temperature instead of spindle speed. To do so, the INDEX pin must have the same number of pulses per minute as the temperature of the hotend in real-time. For example, if the hotend temperature is 150°C in real-time, then the INDEX pin requires 150 pulses per minute to display the temperature of the hotend on Mach3.

As hotend is not able to send the pulses to INDEX pin, the Arduino UNO has been used to read the real-time temperature and send the equivalent pulses to the INDEX pin.

4.2 Development of the temperature control system

As mentioned in section 4.1, it was intended to use the NVEM board's spindle function to regulate the temperature of the hotend. But the VSO output was not enough to control the hotend, nor was it possible to read the temperature from the temperature sensor in real-time directly through this controller board. It was then necessary to use another controller to control the temperature control unit and connect it to the main controller unit (NVEM) so that temperature control via G-code and/or Mach3 would be possible. To do so, the Arduino UNO Board has been used for this purpose. One incentive to use Arduino UNO is that it is open-source so that it can be easy and inexpensive to use in this project as well.

There was already an extruder with the hotend and thermistor in the first prototype. The extruder that has been used in this project is 40w, with NTC100k thermistor. An illustration of how the temperature control system works can be seen in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3 An illustration of the temperature control system

As shown in the illustration, The Arduino UNO powered up by the main controller unit. For this, the 12v to 5v converter is used as a power supply, which can be seen as a black line in the illustration. To set the desired temperature to the hotend, the Arduino UNO can get the input from the VSO pin in a range of 0 to 10v and power up the hotend, which can be seen as the red line in the illustration. The NTC100k thermistor is variable register, Arduino UNO reads the real-time temperature from it using voltage divider circuit. Then it also generates a number of pulses according to the real-time temperature and sends it to the INDEX pin to show the real-time temperature on Mach3, which can be seen as the blue line in an illustration. So the temperature control system is divided into three sections:

4.2.1 Power supply for the Arduino UNO

The Arduino UNO can run on 5v power supply, so it was planned to power it up directly through NVEM controller board instead of using a separate power supply. As mentioned in section 2.6, The NVEM board has a 12v output pin, which has been used to power up the Arduino board. To do so, the power supply circuit has been needed, that converts 12v into 5v. The circuit diagram of this can be seen in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4 The circuit diagram of a power supply

The LM7805 is fixed-voltage regulators. It precisely converts a +12v into +5v and can deliver up to 1.5 A of output current.³³ It is connected between 12v output pin and ground pin of NVEM board through a common diode(1n4148) to prevent damage to NVEM board in case of reverse voltage.

A 100nF capacitor is connected between the input and the ground to reduce the impedance of the input power. It reduces input voltage fluctuations that arise as a result of current demand fluctuations, which cannot be regulated by the voltage regulator. With that, the regulator can keep the output stable when the input is stable. Another 100nF capacitor is connected between the output and the ground to provide a transient response to the output.

As a result, it gives the +5v output between output and ground pins. The series of LED and resistor is connected between output and ground, to see the status of power supply (ON or OFF).

One way to power the Arduino UNO is directly through V_{in} pin, that method has been used in this system. So the output of a power supply circuit connects to the V_{in} and ground pin of Arduino UNO.

4.2.2 Real-time temperature reading

As mentioned in section 4.2, the NTC100k thermistor has been used to read the real-time temperature. The NTC (Negative Temperature Coefficient) thermistor is a variable resistor, their resistance varies with the temperature. In NTC100k, the resistance decreases with an increase in temperature and the resistance increases with a decrease in temperature.

³³ <https://www.sparkfun.com/datasheets/Components/LM7805.pdf>

As the thermistor is a variable resistor, to determine the temperature, the resistance needs to be calculated. The Arduino is unable to measure resistance directly, but it is able to measure the analogue voltage at Analog Pin. In this way, the Arduino measures the voltage at a point between the thermistor and a known resistor using a voltage divider circuit.

The Eq. 4.1 is for a voltage divider, where the V_{out} is a voltage between thermistor and known resistor, V_{in} is the input voltage, R_2 resistance of the known resistor and R_T is the resistance of a thermistor. An Eq. 4.1 becomes Eq. 4.2, by simplifying to solve the thermistor resistance.

$$V_{out} = V_{in} \times \left(\frac{R_T}{R_T + R_2} \right) \tag{Eq. 4.1}$$

$$R_T = R_2 \times \left(\frac{V_{in}}{V_{out}} - 1 \right) \tag{Eq. 4.2}$$

It gives an effective output when the resistor value is approximately equal to the resistance of the thermistor. For this situation, the resistance of the thermistor R_T is 100k Ω , so the resistor R_2 was selected for 100k Ω as well. The circuit diagram of it can be seen in Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5 The circuit diagram of the temperature reading system

So, the Arduino can measure the voltage at Analog Pin (A0), then the Steinhart-Hart equation³⁴ (Eq. 4.3) is used to convert the resistance of the thermistor to a temperature reading. Eq. 4.4 is a simplification of Eq. 4.3, where the T_K is the temperature in Kelvin; A, B, C are Steinhart-Hart coefficients, and R_T is the resistance of a thermistor.

$$\frac{1}{T_K} = A + B \ln R_T + C \ln R_T^3 \quad \text{Eq. 4.3}$$

$$T_K = \frac{1}{A + B \ln R_T + C \ln R_T^3} \quad \text{Eq. 4.4}$$

As the temperature to resistance values of the thermistor was available in the datasheet, it was then easy to calculate Steinhart-Hart coefficients (A, B and C) online platform.^{35 36} So the values of A, B and C for the NTC100k thermistor can be seen in Table 4.2.

Steinhart-Hart coefficients	Value of Steinhart-Hart coefficients
A	1.009249522e-03
B	2.378405444e-04
C	2.019202697e-07

Table 4.2 Steinhart-Hart coefficients (A, B and C) for NTC100k thermistor

As a result, it gives the output in Kelvin, so it was converted in °C using Eq. 4.5.

$$T_C = T_K - 273.15 \quad \text{Eq. 4.5}$$

After this, Arduino determines the real-time temperature of an extruder in °C and can also show it in the serial monitor. To get that on Mach3 through NVEM board, Arduino generates pulses and send it to the INDEX pin through NPN-transistor (s8050) and a voltage divider circuit. The duration of each pulse is 100 milliseconds defined, so it is able to generate 600 pulses in a minute. As NVEM board requires the same number of pulses as real-time temperature value in °C per minute on

³⁴

<https://web.archive.org/web/20110708192840/http://www.cornerstonesensors.com/reports/ABC%20Coefficients%20for%20Steinhart-Hart%20Equation.pdf>

³⁵ http://www.bapihvac.com/wp-content/uploads/2010/11/Thermistor_100K.pdf

³⁶ <https://sanjit.wtf/Calibrator/webCalibrator.html>

INDEX pin to show the real-time temperature on Mach3, the Arduino generate required frequent pulses on a digital output pin 13 (D13).

As mentioned in section 4.1.2, on INDEX pin the pulse voltage needs to be 5-10v, and Arduino is able to give maximum 5v output signal. So the output of Arduino D13 pin has enough voltage for INDEX pin. To solve this issue, another voltage divider circuit has been designed using two resistors with the value $1k\Omega$ and 470Ω , which provides +8.6v. So Arduino pin D13 is connected to the base pin of NPN-transistor (Q1), at each pulse from Arduino, it generates the 8.6v pulse between INDEX and ground pin of NVEM board. A combined circuit diagram of the temperature reading system can be seen in Figure 4.5.

That's how the Mach3 was able to show the real-time temperature of the hotend.

4.2.3 Set the temperature to the hotend

As mentioned in section 4.2, the VSO output is not enough to directly operate the hotend as it can provide output 0v to 10v and a hotend needs minimum 12v to operate. Therefore it was planned to read the desired temperature value from a VSO to Arduino and then Arduino operates the hotend through MOSFET (IRFZ44N). The circuit diagram of the hotend operation system can be seen in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6 The circuit diagram of the hotend operation system

Analog pin of Arduino is able to read the variable voltage value, but it can only read 0-5v. Because of that, it is not possible to read VSO voltage directly through Arduino. To solve this issue, the voltage divider circuit has been designed to read the VSO output voltage, which provides 0-5v according to the 0-10v range. To do so, two resistors (R6 & R7) with the same value (1kΩ) connects in series between VSO and ground pin of NVEM board, so the point between both resistors provides half of the voltage value of the VSO output voltage. That connects between the Arduino Analog pin (A1) and ground pin, with that Arduino can read the variable voltage value of VSO output and convert it into 0 to 1023 value. By that mean, Arduino reads 0°C-300°C as 0-1023 variable. In Arduino programming, it was then converted in the temperature value (T_s) using Eq. 4.6, where the total number of variable at pin A1 is 1024 and maximum temperature value is 300°C. Eq. 4.7 is a simplification of Eq. 4.6.

$$T_s = \frac{\text{Value at pin A1}}{\left(\frac{\text{Total no. of variable at pin A1}}{\text{Max. Temperature value}}\right)} \quad \text{Eq. 4.6}$$

$$T_s = \frac{\text{Value at pin A1}}{\left(\frac{1024}{300}\right)}$$

$$T_s = \frac{\text{Value at pin A1}}{3.41} \quad \text{Eq. 4.7}$$

As a result, Arduino was able to read the value of set temperature (T_s) from VSO pin. So when the spindle speed set on Mach3, then Arduino get it as set temperature (T_s). For example, 180 rpm as 180°C, 250 rpm as 250°C, etc. That value can be also seen on the Arduino serial monitor.

After that, Arduino compares the real-time temperature (T_c) and set temperature (T_s) in a loop, and provides the output at digital pin D09. When the set temperature is lower than the real-time temperature ($T_s < T_c$) then the output on pin D09 is high and when it is equal or higher than the real-time temperature ($T_s \geq T_c$) then the output on pin D09 is low. For the safety reason, the maximum limit of hotend temperature has been set to 300°C. When the real-time temperature is higher than 300 ($T_c > 300$) then the output on pin D09 is low too.

As Arduino can provide 5v maximum on a digital pin D09 as an output, it was necessary to provide separate power supply to the hotend. To operate the hotend with separate power supply using Arduino, the NPN-transistor (s8050) and N-channel MOSFET (IRFZ44N) was connected to the output of the Arduino (D09). So the Arduino output operates the transistor (Q2) and transistor (Q2) operates the MOSFET (Q3), then MOSFET (Q3) operates the ground of hotend with power supply. The IRFZ44N MOSFET is able to operate with high voltage and high current, therefore it was selected to operate the hotend. The connection of the hotend with power supply and with Arduino can be seen in the circuit diagram (Figure 4.6).

That's how the Mach3 was able to set the temperature to the hotend.

4.3 Hardware design

Before designing the hardware PCB, it was necessary to test the circuit on a breadboard. To do so, all components have been connected on a breadboard for all three circuits.

4.3.1 Breadboard connection

The breadboard connection can be seen in Figure 4.7. Components and circuit shown in a green box are for a power supply, for the hotend operating system is in orange boxes, and for the real-time temperature reading system is in blue boxes.

Figure 4.7 also indicates all the connections that connecting to the Arduino and NVEM boards.

Figure 4.7 The breadboard connection of all components

On breadboard connection, all circuits provided consistent outputs. So it was then decided to design a combined circuit of those all three circuits. In Figure 4.8, the final circuit diagram with all circuit combinations can be seen.

Figure 4.8 The final circuit diagram with all circuit combinations

4.3.2 PCB design and fabrication

The PCB was designed according to the final circuit diagram on the Fritzing, which can be seen in Appendix B. The final version of the PCB was designed after several improvements and adjustments in a first design, which can be seen in Figure 4.9.

Figure 4.9 The front- (at left) and back-side (at right) of the final PCB design

Figure 4.10 The final fabricated PCB (front at left side and back at right side)

The final PCB module has been designed as two-layer PCB, to remove jumpers and to fit screw terminal block instead of normal female junctions. The shape/dimension of the PCB was selected as same as Arduino UNO, therefore it can be directly installed/connected on Arduino UNO board. The final fabricated PCB, before and after shouldering the components can be seen in Figure 4.10 and Figure 4.11.

Figure 4.11 The final fabricated PCB with shouldered components (front at left side and back at right side)

4.4 Programming

The Arduino had to be programmed as the temperature control system is based on Arduino, to read real-time temperature and to set the hotend to the appropriate temperature value. The Arduino IDE was used to write, compile and upload the program on the Arduino board. The program is divided into three parts: the declaration of global variables, the setup code, and the loop code.

4.4.1 The declaration of global variables

Global variables are defined at the top of the program from line 2 to 18. Throughout the duration of the program, the global variables will retain their value. Any function in the entire program after its declaration can access a global variable.

```

1.  /* The temperature control system */
2.  int ThermistorPin = A0;      //Thermistor input connected to Analog pin 0
3.  int VSOPin = A1;           //VSO output connected to Analog pin 1
4.  int ExtPin = 9;            //Extruder output connected to PWM pin 9
5.  const int IndexPin = 13;    //Index pin connected to digital pin 13
6.  int varS = 0;              //variable to store the read value varS
7.  int varR = 0;              //variable to store the read value varR
8.  int PulseState = LOW;      //PulseState set to low at starting
9.
10. unsigned long previousMillis = 0;    //update previous pulse to zero
11. unsigned long OnTime = 100;          //high value of pulse in ms
12. unsigned long OffTime = 50900;      //low value of pulse in ms
13. unsigned long Tc;
14. unsigned long Ts;
15.
16. float R2 = 10000;                    //Resistor defined
17. float logRT, RT, T;
18. float A=1.009249522e-03, B=2.378405444e-04, C=2.019202697e-07;
    //Steinhart-Hart coefficients

```

Integers are defined as `int` from line 2 to 8. As the value of the thermistor and VSO pin had to be read through Analog pin 0 and 1, it has been defined as `ThermistorPin` and `VSOPin` simultaneously. The extruder and Index pulses connected to Digital pin 9 and 13, so it was defined as `ExtPin` and `IndexPin`. Variables `varS`, `varR` and `PulseState` are defined to use in the loop function, all three are set to low before runs the loop function.

As there run two functions simultaneously in one program, to generate pulsed for Index pin the `millis()` function had been used in the program. With that, it was easy to generate pules without interfering other function on loop. To use the millis function, `unsigned long` variables are defined from line 10 to 14. On the base of pulses per minute, 100ms time for the pulse value high and 50900ms time for the pulse value low has been decided and as `unsigned long` variables `OnTime` and `OffTime` defined. Because the variable `Tc` (real-time temperature) and `Ts` (set temperature) are being in used with `millis()` function, those are also defined as `unsigned long`.

As `float` variables can store 32 bits (4 bytes) of information, the Steinhart-Hart coefficients (`A`, `B` and `C`) are defined as `float` variables. The value of Steinhart-

Hart coefficients has been defined as per Table 4.2. Variables **R2**, **logRT**, **RT** and **T** are being used with float variables, and so it has been also defined as **float** variables.

4.4.2 The setup code

For initializing variables and pin modes the setup function is used, it has been defined in line 19 to 26. After each power up or reset of the Arduino board, the **setup()** function will run only once.

```

19. void setup()
20. {
21.   Serial.begin(9600);
22.   pinMode(ThermistorPin, INPUT);           //sets ThermistorPin as output
23.   pinMode(VSOPin, INPUT);                 //sets VSOPin as output
24.   pinMode(IndexPin, OUTPUT);              //sets IndexPin as output
25.   pinMode(ExtPin, OUTPUT);                //sets ExtPin as output
26. }

```

To show the output on the serial monitor of Arduino IDE, the **Serial.begin()** function has defined at 9600 bits per second data rate. After that, **ThermistorPin** and **VSOPin** have defined as **INPUT**; and **IndexPin** and **ExtPin** have defined as **OUTPUT**.

4.4.3 The loop code

The loop code Executed right after setup code, which starts from line 27. The **loop()** function runs consecutively, it used to do the main task of the program and to control the Arduino board.

```

27. void loop()
28. {
29.   varR = analogRead(ThermistorPin); //read the input from Thermistorpin
30.   RT = R2 * (1023.0 / (float)varR - 1.0);
31.   logRT = log(RT);
32.   T = (1.0 / (A + B * logRT + C * logRT * logRT * logRT));
33.   Tc = T - 273.15;
34.   varS = analogRead(VSOPin);           //read the input from VSO pin
35.   Ts = map(varS,0,1023,30,300);

```

As mentioned in section 4.2.2, pin A0 read the value of **ThermistorPin** and store it in variable **varR**. After that, as per the Eq. 4.2, it calculates the value of variable **RT**. Then as per the Steinhart-Hart equation (Eq. 4.3), it calculates the real-time

temperature in Kelvin and stores it in variable **T**. The conversion of temperature from Kelvin to °C has been programmed as per Eq. 4.5, and store it in variable **Tc**.

As mentioned in section 4.2.3, pin A1 read the value of **VSOPin** and store it in variable **varS**. After that, the **map()** function was used to calculates the value of set temperature and stores it in variable **Ts**. the **map()** function maps the value of variable **varS** from 0-1023 range to 30-300 range. The 30-300 range was selected instead of the 0-300 to get a better result.

```

36.  if (Ts > Tc)
37.  {
38.    analogWrite(ExtPin, 0);
39.  }
40.  else                                //(varR<=varS)
41.  {
42.    analogWrite(ExtPin, 255);
43.  }
44.  if (Tc > 300)
45.  {
46.    analogWrite(ExtPin, 0);
47.  }

```

In order to compare the real-time temperature (**Tc**) and the set temperature (**Ts**) to cause the **ExtPin** pin as per conditions, the **if** and **else** functions are used. As mentioned in section 4.2.3, the condition (**Ts > Tc**) has been defined in the **if** function, that gives **0** output at **ExtPin** when it is true, else it gives **255** (High) output at **ExtPin**. The maximum limit of hotend temperature has been defined to 300°C, as when the condition (**Tc > 300**) is true in if function then it sets the **ExtPin** to **0**.

```

48.  Serial.print("Set Temperature: ");          //Serial-print Set Temp.:
49.  Serial.print(Ts);                          //Set Temperature value
50.  Serial.println(" C");
51.  Serial.print(" Real Temperature: ");        //Serial-print Real Temp.:
52.  Serial.print(Tc);                          //Real Temperature value
53.  Serial.println(" C");

```

The **Serial.print()** and **Serial.println()** functions are used to print the real-time temperature (**Tc**) and the set temperature (**Ts**) on the serial monitor of Arduino IDE, to see that values during the testing the system.

```

54.  unsigned long currentMillis = millis();    //Call millis function
55.  if ((PulseState == HIGH)&&(currentMillis - previousMillis >= OnTime))
56.  {
57.    PulseState = LOW;                       //Low Pulse
58.    previousMillis = currentMillis;         //Remember the time
59.    digitalWrite(IndexPin, PulseState);    //Update the actual Pulse value
60.  }
61.  else if ((PulseState==LOW)&&(currentMillis-previousMillis >=
    (OffTime/Tc)))

```

```
62.  {
63.    PulseState = HIGH;           //High Pulse
64.    previousMillis = currentMillis; //Remember the time
65.    digitalWrite(IndexPin, PulseState); //Update the actual Pulse value
66.  }
67. }
```

As mentioned above, the `millis()` function has been used to generate pulsed for `IndexPin` without interfering to other function of the program. By `unsigned long currentMillis = millis()`, the `millis` function has been activated/called in the program. In `millis` function, the `currentMillis` always increases up to 4,294,967,295. To generate pulse as per the requirement, the `OffTime` needs to be varied.

Therefore, two conditions `((PulseState == HIGH) && (currentMillis - previousMillis >= OnTime))` have been defined in `if` function, that sets `IndexPin` at `LOW` when conditions are true, where the difference between `currentMillis` and `previousMillis` compares with `OnTime`. The same logic also applied to `else if` function too, where the two conditions `(PulseState==LOW) && (currentMillis-previousMillis >= (OffTime/Tc))` have been defined, to set the `IndexPin` at `HIGH`. But here, as the variable `Tc` varies the condition `(currentMillis-previousMillis >= (OffTime/Tc))` also varies, and that provides the required time duration between pulses.

As a result, Arduino generates the same number of pulses per minute on `IndexPin` that the real-time temperature value has and sets the required temperature value on `ExtPin`.

Chapter 5 Result and Discussion

The results of the calibration of additional two axes of 5-axial system and the result of the temperature control system will be presented and analysed in this chapter. It includes a general discussion of the outcome of the additional axes and the temperature control system in the 5-axis 3D printer.

5.1 Result of calibration system of 5-axial 3D printer

The calibration of both additional axes and the overall calibration of the printer has been done as per mention in section 3.5. The rotational movement of the B- and C-axis was tested, and the accuracy of the home position at the system's origin has also been examined to evaluate the calibration system results.

5.1.1 Testing the B-axis

The rotational movement of B-axis was tested with the sample G-code that rotates the hotend and positioned it at different angles. The B-axis was moved from -90° to 90° with a 45° angle difference at each step. The system was tested by running the sequence several times, the G-code to test B-axis can be seen in the G-code 5.1, to make sure this system is accurate enough to be used over time.

```
1. G0 B0
2. G0 B45
3. G0 B90
4. G0 B45
5. G0 B0
6. G0 B-45
7. G0 B-90
8. G0 B-45
9. G0 B0
```

G-code 5.1 G-code to test B-axis movement

The results of this can be seen in Figure 5.1 and Figure 5.2, shows the different angular position of the hotend along the B-axis from the test. This shows the extruder's precise and stable rotational movement at the specified angular value, which is commanded by the G-code. Due to the inaccurate fitting of the head rotary system, there is some angular error after a long runs that can be seen in Table 5.1.

Figure 5.1 Result of B-axis tests at 0°, 45° and 90° (from left to right)

Figure 5.2 Result of B-axis tests at 0°, -45° and -90° (from left to right)

	Angular value of the hotend				
<i>At starting</i>	90°	45°	0°	-45°	-90°
<i>1st run</i>	90°	45°	0°	-45°	-90°
<i>2nd run</i>	90°	45°	0°	-45°	-89.5°
<i>3rd run</i>	90.5°	45.5°	0.5°	-44.5°	-89°
<i>4th run</i>	90°	45°	0°	-44.5°	-89.5°

Table 5.1 The angular error after a long run of B-axis

The result shows that it has -0.5° to -1° angular error in B- direction and up to +0.5° angular error in +B direction because of cables that attached with the extruder and inaccurate attachment of the extruder on mount section of the Head rotary system. Since this value of the error is minimal, it is considered appropriate.

5.1.2 Testing the C-axis

The rotational movement of C-axis was tested similar as B-axis, with the sample G-code that rotates the print bed and positioned it at different angles. The C-axis was rotated from -360° to 360° with a 45° angle difference at each step by running

the sequence of G-code several times, the G-code to test C-axis can be seen in the G-code 5.2, to make sure this system is accurate enough to be used over time.

```
1. G0 C-360
2. G0 C-270
3. G0 C-225
4. G0 C-180
5. G0 C-135
6. G0 C-90
7. G0 C-45
8. G0 C0
9. G0 C45
10. G0 C90
11. G0 C135
12. G0 C180
13. G0 C225
14. G0 C270
15. G0 C360
```

G-code 5.2 G-code to test C-axis movement

The results of this can be seen in Figure 5.3 and Figure 5.4, showing from the tests the different angular position of the print bed along the C-axis. This shows the print bed's precise and stable rotational movement at the specified angular value, which is commanded by the G-code. The result was very precise without any error at different runs that can be seen in Table 5.2.

Figure 5.3 Result of C-axis tests at 0°, 45° and 135° (from left to right)

Figure 5.4 Result of C-axis tests at 180°, 270° and 360° (from left to right)

	Angular value of the print bed						
At starting	360°	270°	180°	90°	0°	-180°	-360°
1 st run	360°	270°	180°	90°	0°	-180°	-360°
2 nd run	360°	270°	180°	90°	0°	-180°	-360°
3 rd run	360°	270°	180°	90°	0°	-180°	-360°
4 th run	360°	270°	180°	90°	0°	-180°	-360°

Table 5.2 The result of C-axis after a long run

The result shows that, without any angular error, it provides precise C-axis rotational movement in both CW and CCW directions.

5.1.3 Testing the calibration of the home position/origin

As mentioned in section 3.5, after defining the home position for all axes the hotend positioned itself at the centre of the print bed before the starting of the printing process. The home position after each linear and rotational movement of each axis was examined with two sample G-codes to find the accuracy of the origin of the system and alignment of both rotary axes after several runs. By G-code 5.3, the system provides X-, Y- and Z-axial linear movement in both directions and B- and C-axial rotational movement in a step-by-step manner, between each movement the system positioned itself at the origin. The system was examined each time when the system positioned itself at the origin.

- | | |
|----|---------------------|
| 1. | G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B0 C0 |
| 2. | G1 X10 Y0 Z0 B0 C0 |
| 3. | G1 X-10 Y0 Z0 B0 C0 |
| 4. | G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B0 C0 |
| 5. | G1 X0 Y10 Z0 B0 C0 |
| 6. | G1 X0 Y-10 Z0 B0 C0 |
| 7. | G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B0 C0 |

```

8.  G1 X0 Y0 Z10 B0 C0
9.  G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B0 C0
10. G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B90 C0
11. G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B-90 C0
12. G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B0 C0
13. G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B0 C360
14. G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B0 C0

```

G-code 5.3 G-code to examine the origin after each axial movement

By G-code 5.4, the system provides simultaneous movement of all axes continuously and positioned itself at the origin again at the end. The system was examined by running the G-code several times, to make sure this system is accurate enough to be used over time.

```

1.  G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B0 C0
2.  G1 X10 Y0 Z0 B0 C0
3.  G1 X0 Y10 Z0 B0 C0
4.  G1 X0 Y0 Z10 B0 C0
5.  G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B45 C0
6.  G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B0 C0
7.  G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B-45 C0
8.  G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B0 C180
9.  G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B0 C-180
10. G1 X0 Y0 Z0 B0 C0

```

G-code 5.4 G-code to examine the origin after all axial movement

The results of G-code 5.3 can be seen in Figure 5.5, shows the position of the system origin (Home position) at the beginning of the G-code at left and after the ending of G-code at right. This shows the precise positioning of the origin after the system had several runs.

Figure 5.5 System origin before run (at left) and after run (at right)

The results of G-code 5.4 can be seen in Figure 5.6 and Figure 5.7, shows the movement of each axis step-by-step as per the G-code sequence. The position of the system origin (Home position) before the G-code started can be seen in the first photo (at left) of Figure 5.6 and the resultant position of the system origin after the G-code ended can be seen in the last photo (at right) of Figure 5.7. This also shows the precise positioning of the origin and movement of all axes after the system had several runs.

Figure 5.6 Position of both rotary systems at each step of G-code 5.4

Figure 5.7 Position of both rotary systems at each step of G-code 5.4

The result shows that it provides a precise outcome of the extruder's position at the centre of the table rotary system after several runs of G-code, without any error.

5.2 Result of the temperature control system

The temperature control system has been tested with the G-code of the spindle function on Mach3 to set the hot-end temperature. The accuracy of the set-temperature and the reading of the real-time temperature by the Arduino has also been examined by the Arduino IDE serial display. For that, the final PCB module has been connected with Arduino and NVEM board, which can be seen in Figure 5.8. That provides the output for the hotend to set the temperature by G-code and/or also via Mach3 spindle function and the input-pulses for the INDEX pin to get the real-time temperature on Mach3.

The test was done by the sample G-code that set the hotend temperature at different values. The spindle speed was set at 100 to 300 rpm with a 50 rpm difference at each step. The temperature control system was tested by running the sequence several times without actual connection of the hotend, the G-code to set the hotend temperature can be seen in the G-code 5.5. As the hotend was not connected for safety purposes during each sequence of G-code, the result of this was observed on the serial monitor of the Arduino IDE.

Figure 5.8 The connection of a final PCB module with Arduino and NVEM board for testing

```

1. M03
2. S100
3. S150
4. S200
5. S250
6. S300
7. M05

```

G-code 5.5 the G-code to set the hotend temperature

The results of this can be seen in Figure 5.9, Figure 5.10, Figure 5.11, Figure 5.12 and Figure 5.13; that shows the set-temperature at different input values of spindle rpm by G-code.

When the spindle speed was set to 100, then the hotend was set to 94° C as the set temperature and the spindle speed was set to 150 rpm, then the hotend was set to 148° -149° C as the set temperature. That data was seen on the serial monitor, which can be seen in Figure 5.9 and Figure 5.10.

When the spindle speed was set to 200, then the hotend was set to 176°-177° C as the set temperature and the spindle speed was set to 250 rpm, then the hotend was set to 246° -247° C as the set temperature. That data was seen on the serial monitor, which can be seen in Figure 5.11 and Figure 5.12.

Figure 5.9 Result as S100 G-code

Figure 5.10 Result as S150 G-code

Figure 5.11 Result as S200 G-code

Figure 5.12 Result as S250 G-code

When the spindle speed was set to 300, then the hotend was set to 300° C as the set temperature. That data was seen on the serial monitor, which can be seen in Figure 5.13.

Figure 5.13 Result as S300 G-code

The result shows that it provides a more accurate output at high-temperature value as it gradually decreases the difference between the input value and output value.

Since this system has to operate mainly at 250° C or more, the accuracy was considered appropriate at this value.

To read the real-time temperature on Mach3, the PCB module provides the pulses to INDEX pin of the NVEM board. After the configuration of the INDEX function for NVEM board has been done on Mach3, the system was not able to convert the pulses per minute to rpm (real-time temperature). But since the system was able to set the hotend temperature and as it operates in an Arduino feedback loop and as the maximum temperature limit was also defined by Arduino, this system was considered appropriate at this point.

Chapter 6 Conclusion and Future outlook

This chapter will conclude this research and discuss the opportunity for the future outlook for the 5-axial 3D printer.

6.1 Conclusion

This thesis asks, in section 1.2, whether it is possible to develop a calibration system for the 5-axis 3D printer with two additional axes to a 3-axial 3D printer and to develop a temperature control system for it. During this study, two additional axes were designed, calibrated and tested; and the temperature control system was developed, programmed and tested for the second prototype of the 5-axial printer. This has been accomplished after studying the 5-axial 3D printer's first prototype. Besides, the PCB module for the temperature control system was created to control the hotend temperature by the spindle function of the Novusun NVEM board, which can eliminate the system's manual temperature control.

The 5-axial 3D printer that has been developed is still a prototype and there are still some errors in the calibration of the head rotary system and the temperature control system, as mentioned in Chapter 5. Despite these issues, this study has demonstrated that by installing a rotary system to a 3-axial printer, it is possible to construct a 5-axial printer. It has also been demonstrated that the hotend temperature can be regulated by G-code for the NVEM board's spindle function, although there is still some issue to see the real-time temperature on Mach3.

However, the possibility to print an object with this system can be distinguished after do some printing testing with this system. But as this project was about to develop a calibration system, the printing process should be an attempt to see the final result of this system. From the results of the calibration system and the temperature control system, it can be concluded that both of the key goals of the project have been accomplished and the project has thus been a success.

Besides that, there is still a lot of research to be developed for the 5-axial 3D printer to be economically feasible. The lack of a slicer and firmware for 5-axial 3D printing is one of the big problems. It is hoped that this thesis would promote interest in 5-axial 3D printing technologies and will raise interest in the development of multi-axial 3D printers and slicers.

6.2 Future outlook

It became noticeable during the work on this project that the system still has space for improvements that should be discussed in future outlook.

The use of another controller with features for a 3D printer instead of a CNC machine would be one of the key enhancements to this system. The system will not be as constrained by doing this as it is now. The possibility of setting the hotend temperature using the G-code of a 3D printer will be provided by a controller unit that has support for 3D printers. Besides, the printer will be able to get a G-code directly through the slicer that has a specialty in 3D printing technology. The B- and C- axis should also be tested with a more accurate measuring tool. According to the origin of the system, the positioning of the Y-axis mechanism can be rearranged so that the print bed and the extruder will have equal jog distance in both directions of X- and Y-axis accordingly. To make sure it is as accurate as possible, the system can be modified.

Different parameters should be examined, such as layer height and speed of the printing process. In this system, the B-axis has a limitation of rotational movement of 90° in both directions for the extruder, which can also be checked to increase the angle of the rotational movement for the extruder.

The use of another controller unit and firmware can improve the system performance and allow an auto-calibration mode for the rotary axes. There are some options for this. For example, the Duet3 mainboard³⁷ with an extension.

³⁷ <https://www.duet3d.com/Duet3Mainboard6HC>

Bibliography

Appendix A

Appendix B